

R&I PEERS

Pilot experiences for improving gender equality in research organisations

Start date of project: 1st May 2018

Duration: 48 months

D7.7– First RRI validation reporting

WP n° and title	WP7 – Dissemination and Impact creation
Responsible Author(s)	Fernando Ferri (CNR), Patrizia Grifoni (CNR), Chiara Bicchielli (CNR), Noemi Biancone (CNR)
Contributor(s)	Angela Amaturò (AISAI); Andreas Andreou (CNTI); Amani Charrad (ANPRT); Alessia D’Andrea (CNR); Che Van Dyck (DLI); Sigal Fishman (MIGAL); Tiziana Guzzo (CNR); Nagore Ibarra (CIC nanoGUNE); Katja Legisa (DLI); Katerina Loukidou (GSFPGE); Uri Marchaim (MIGAL); Maria Rosaria Pelizzari (UNISA-OGPEO), Loredana Incarnato (UNISA-OGPEO); Debora Sarnelli (UNISA-OGPEO); Daniela Sica (UNISA-OGPEO); Tanja Petrovic (ZRC SAZU); Dimitris Platis (GSFPGE)
Version	v.01

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 788171

Deliverable information

Status (F: final; D: draft; RD: revised draft):	F
Planned delivery date	30/04/2020 (M24)
Actual delivery date	26/05/2020
Dissemination level: (PU = Public; PP = Restricted to other program participants; RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium; CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium)	PU
Type: Report, Website, Other, Ethics	Report

Document History

Version	Date (MM/DD/YYYY)	Created/Amended by	Changes
01	03/03/2020	Fernando Ferri (CNR); Patrizia Grifoni (CNR); Noemi Biancone (CNR); Chiara Bicchielli (CNR)	Definition of the section of the survey on Ethics, definition of the overall survey, definition and configuration of the on-line framework for collecting information
02	04/04/2020	Alessia D'Andrea (CNR); Tiziana Guzzo (CNR)	Contributed in defining a revised version of the overall survey
03	04/08/2020	Loredana Incarnato (UNISA-OGPEO); Maria Rosaria Pelizzari (UNISA-OGPEO)	Contributed in defining a revised version of the overall survey
04	04/12/2020	Katja Legisa (DLI); Che Van Dyck (DLI)	Contribution in the survey definition for the Gender equality dimension
05	04/12/2020	Tanja Petrovic (ZRC SAZU)	Contribution in the survey definition for Science education

06	04/12/2020	Andreas Andreou (CNTI)	Contribution in the survey definition for Public Engagement
07	04/12/2020	Sigal Fishman (MIGAL); Uri Marchaim (MIGAL)	Contribution in the survey definition for Open Access
08	30/04/2020	Fernando Ferri (CNR); Patrizia Grifoni (CNR); Noemi Biancone (CNR); Chiara Bicchielli (CNR)	Final version of the overall survey framework
09	10/05/2020	Angela Amaturro (AISAI); Andreas Andreou (CNTI); Amani Charrad (ANPRT); Fernando Ferri (CNR); Sigal Fishman (MIGAL); Nagore Ibarra (CIC nanoGUNE); Loredana Incarnato (UNISA-OGPEO); Katja Legisa (DLI); Katerina Loukidou (GSFPGE); Uri Marchaim (MIGAL); Maria Rosaria Pelizzari (UNISA-OGPEO); Tanja Petrovic (ZRC SAZU); Dimitris Platis (GSFPGE) Debora Sarnelli (UNISA- OGPEO); Daniela Sica (UNISA- OGPEO)	Provided data on RRI with respect to their organization
10	20/05/2020	Fernando Ferri (CNR); Patrizia Grifoni (CNR); Noemi Biancone (CNR); Chiara Bicchielli (CNR)	Added sections related with data collected, their descriptions and the final comments
11	21/05/2020	Fernando Ferri (CNR)	Revision of the overall document

12	26/05/2020	Amani Charrad (ANPRT); Sigal Fishman (MIGAL); Nagore Ibarra (CIC nanoGUNE); Katja Legisa (DLI); Katerina Loukidou (GSFPGE); Maria Rosaria Pelizzari (UNISA-OGPEO); Tanja Petrovic (ZRC SAZU); Dimitris Platis (GSFPGE) Debora Sarnelli (UNISA- OGPEO); Daniela Sica (UNISA-OGPEO)	Revised the document before the final submission
13	27/05/2020	Fernando Ferri (CNR); Patrizia Grifoni (CNR)	Production of the final document

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1 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CUG	Comitato Unico di Garanzia
EC	European Commission
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
H2020	Horizon 2020
OGEPO	Inter-departmental Observatory for Gender studies and Gender Equality (Osservatorio interdipartimentale per gli studi di Genere e le Pari Opportunità)
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

2 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the first results of the monitoring activities in R&I Peers related to the five pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation that European Commission identified for RRI [1], i.e. Ethics, Gender equality, Open access, Public engagement, Science education, as planned in the task “T7.4 RRI validation check”. For this purpose, a survey was defined and carried out. This survey collects data for the validation check concerning the adoption of the principles of Responsible Research and innovation during the activities of the project. This is following the Task 7.4 "RRI validation check" of "WP7– Dissemination and impact creation". This task is monitoring that the five pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation are kept accordingly to the definitions and indications of the European Commission.

In particular, CNR defined a first version of the survey related to the inclusion of RRI in the R&I-PEERS project, based on the experiences, knowledge and concepts from other RRI projects such as the MARINA project. Specifically, CNR put also a particular focus on ethical issues. The draft survey was shared with CNTI, DLI, MIGAL, ZRC SAZU and UNISA that contributed in revising the draft, providing their specific contribution with respect to the Gender, Open access, Public engagement and Science education.

All the members of the R&I-PEERS consortium filled-in the questionnaire for the survey and, data were analysed by CNR. The results of this analysis are presented in the section related to the “Analysis of the collected data”. In particular, section 3.1 contains the questionnaire partners that are implementing the GEP, while section 3.2 contains the questionnaire for partners that are not implementing the GEP in R&I-PEERS. Indeed, the questionnaire addressed to the partners that are implementing the GEP in R&I-PEERS consists of two parts: “Part 1 – Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project (not directly connected to the activities carried out in the GEP), related to your organisation” and “Part 2 - Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project, related to your GEP activities”. The R&I-PEERS partners that are not implementing the GEP are asked to fill in the questionnaire containing one part only about “Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project, related to your organisation”.

Here, a short description of the concepts related to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is provided. RRI is a new perspective for research and society adopting a holistic and multidisciplinary perspective in the activity implementation and behaviours, aiming to implement a stronger collaboration among the different actors of the quadruple helix, i.e. research institutions and universities, industries, policymakers and citizens. These actors are engaged in working together during the research and innovation process, aiming at aligning the project activities and its outcomes with values, needs and expectations of the different actors and society.

The five thematic pillars of RRI [1] are synthetically described below.

Ethics

“For all activities funded by the European Union, ethics is an integral part of research from beginning to end, and ethical compliance is seen as pivotal to achieve real research excellence.

The most common ethical issues include:

- the involvement of children, patients, vulnerable populations,
- the use of human embryonic stem cells,
- privacy and data protection issues,
- research on animals and non-human primates.

It also includes the avoidance of any breach of research integrity, which means, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct” [5].

Gender

“In Horizon 2020 Gender is a cross-cutting issue and is mainstreamed in each of the different parts of the Work Programme, ensuring a more integrated approach to research and innovation.

Three objectives underpin the strategy on gender equality in Horizon 2020:

- Fostering gender balance in research teams, to close the gaps in terms of participation.
- Ensuring gender balance in decision-making, to reach the target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups and of 50% in advisory groups.
- Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content helps improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation” [4].

Open access

“The global shift towards making research findings available free of charge for readers, so-called 'Open access', has been a core strategy in the European Commission to improve knowledge circulation and thus innovation. It is illustrated in particular by the general principle for open access to scientific publications in Horizon 2020 and the pilot for research data.” [3]

Public engagement

“Public engagement (PE) in Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is about co-creating the future with citizens and civil society organisations, and also bringing on board the widest possible diversity of actors that would not normally interact with each other, on matters of science and technology.” [2]

Science education

“Building capacities and developing innovative ways of connecting science to society is a priority under Horizon 2020. This will help to make science more attractive to young people, increase society's appetite for innovation, and open up further research and innovation activities.

Making science education and careers attractive to young people is an ambitious goal since it targets to drastically improve science and technology-literacy in our society.

Innovative formal and informal science education teaching and learning are important in order to raise both young boys' and girls' awareness of the different aspects encompassing science and technology in today's society and to address the challenges faced by young people when pursuing careers in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

Therefore, a sustainable and cross-cutting interaction between the relevant actors in the field is crucial” [6].

3 DEFINITION OF THE SURVEY

This survey aims to analyse how the five pillars RRI - i.e. Ethics, Gender equality, Open access, Public engagement and Science education - are kept in the activities of the R&I-PEERS project accordingly to the guidelines of the European Commission (EC).

RRI addresses research and the project activities according to an approach that has to be safe, ethically acceptable, and responding to the societal and people needs and expectations and, it aims at aligning research and innovation changes within societal values.

The EC defines RRI [1] as “a process where all societal actors (researchers, citizens, policymakers, business, third sector organisations etc.) work together during the whole R&I process to better align R&I outcomes to the values, needs and expectations of European society. “RRI consists of designing and implementing R&I policy that will:

- o engage society more broadly in its research and innovation activities,
- o increase access to scientific results,
- o ensure gender equality, in both the research process and research content,
- o take into account the ethical dimension, and
- o promote formal and informal science education” [7].

The question that we are answering as a consortium of the R&I-PEERS project is the following:

Why observing the R&I-PEERS Project implementation under the lens of RRI?

This is because RRI enables "governing innovation through early 'upstream' interventions rather than 'downstream' monitoring and 'correction' of interventions ex-post" [8]. This means that the approach followed in planning and carrying out the R&I-PEERS project activities adopts the five RRI pillars. The survey will also stimulate the R&I-PEERS consortium to improve the RRI approach adoption along with the project life.

In particular, this survey about the RRI adoption and validation in R&I-PEERS has been administrated both: 1) to the five pilot organizations (Research Performing Organizations, and Research Funding Organizations) and, 2) to the other partners of the consortium.

All the consortium members are asked to contribute to this data collection. Each partner fills in only one time the questionnaire based on the information and opinions of the staff that is working in the R&I-PEERS project. Indeed, the answer can be discussed internally by each organisation and one person will provide the answer for the organisation.

The survey is different for organisations that are implementing the GEPs (pilot organisations) and the other partners that are not implementing them. In particular, pilot organisations are invited to provide both, 1) information on Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project (not directly connected to the activities carried out in the GEP), related to your organisation, 2) information on the use of the Responsible Research and Innovation principles in the R&I-PEERS project, related to your GEP activities, while partners that do not implement the GEP will be invited to provide only information on RRI related to their activity in the project. Appendix I describes the questionnaire filled in by the pilot partners and the questionnaire filled in by the remaining partners of the R&I-PEERS consortium. The survey can be also filled in on-line at: <https://www.riggep.eu/registeredarea/rriSurvey> (for more details, please see Appendix II).

4 ANALYSIS OF THE COLLECTED DATA

This section is structured in sub-sections that provide an analysis of information collected from the R&I-PEERS partners. In particular, piloting partners provided answers to the questionnaire, also in relation with the activities carried out within the GEPs activities, while the other partners provided their answers only based on the situation in their organisation and the behaviour during the implementation of the R&I-PEERS project activities (not included in the GEPs).

4.1 UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO (UNISA-OGEPO)

The University of Salerno is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. UNISA is familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and, has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities, in particular applying ethical principles and satisfying GDPR requirements.

The University already has a public ethical code (available online at: <https://web.unisa.it/uploads/rescue/41/76/2017-10-25---DR-codice-etico.pdf>) and the team involved in R&I-PEERS is very aware of the rules established in it (“Good Research Practices” followed by UNISA-OGEPO are available at: <http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>). The ethical rules have been taken into account applying a responsible process of communication and information during R&I-PEERS activities, asking each time for an informed consent for images or personal data and managing data following National, European laws and GDPR.

The activities in R&I-PEERS within the GEP are producing an important evolution in behaviours, as involved in the discussions carried on about gender not only by women. Moreover, improved awareness about gender issues produced a wider collaboration between scientific fields and humanities. The effect was to stimulate the equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members that feel this perspective very stimulating and beneficial.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, the University involved staff members of any gender in the staff project, to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives as part of GEP implementation. Moreover, UNISA with the support of OGEPO, made an effort for the creation of family-friendly workspaces, providing a nursery and pink parking spaces for women and men with children and promoting the possibility for the employees to benefit from parental leave. Furthermore, the University has also succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, the University of Salerno provided only some project’s outputs freely accessible: Newsletters, Public Deliverables (after the approval of the Project Officer and the Commission) and Posters produced within the project. Internal documents of the R&I-PEERS Consortium (such as meeting minutes, working documents) and the confidential deliverables were not made public. The University of Salerno did not establish Open Access practices to follow and, at the moment, the R&I-PEERS team of the University did not make open accessible the defined GEP, but it will be made accessible as soon as within the final version.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, the University of Salerno carried out 31 different public engagement activities involving very frequently people external to the organization can be considered satisfying and Beneficial. The initiatives of the University of Salerno with the support of the OGEPO team, were addressed to strengthen the local network with industries and stakeholders, thanks to a bond the University has with the Salerno Female Committee of the Italian Industrial Federation and with the Councillor of Equal Opportunities of the Campania Region. Moreover, UNISA had a continuous exchange of best practices and ideas with the National Committees for equal opportunities (in Italian “Comitati Unici di Garanzia - CUG), at regional and national level and, with other local stakeholders and associations (such as FIDAPA, the councillor for culture of the Municipality of Salerno, Salerno Literature festival). Step by step, UNISA is implementing the local network promoting gender-sensitive projects and events disseminating them through radio, magazines, television programs and blogs. The outcomes produced by the exchanges with networks (from local to the international level) are stimulating the improvement of the diffusion of gender in training, and gender-awareness campaigns have been triggered.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, the University of Salerno is active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy also with the contribution of the R&I-PEERS project, by facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange in the field of gender equality. Some science education activities organised are: 1) the first Master on GE (Leadership, Gender Equality, Diversity Opportunity “LEGEnDO”) approved on April 7, 2020, by the Department of Humanities Board of Professors and 2) the teaching of “Women’s History and Gender Studies” open to students of all disciplines and departments, but also initiatives such as 3) the fundraising campaign addressed to national enterprises, institutions and associations “ADOPT A TALENT, for gender equity” to help talented students. The University community (internal and external) shows a growing interest in gender-related events and has actively taken part in seminars and workshops promoted by the R&I-PEERS team concerning gender-sensitive issues. These educational actions were considered beneficial as they helped unhinge some rigid patterns that have traditionally defined relationships, choices and power relationships between women and men. New relationship models in which both women and men must rethink themselves are necessary.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<i>Ethical and research integrity principles in the Grant Agreement (article 34) WP 1 Ethics requirements and relative deliverables D1.1, D1.2, D1.3</i>	

<i>GDPR requirements for the R&I-PEERS platform and informed consent for platform users</i>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
Yes	
if Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.	
<i>Ethical code UNISA available at the following link: https://web.unisa.it/uploads/rescue/41/76/2017-10-25---DR-codice-etico.pdf</i>	
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?	
<i>Very aware</i>	
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Please see “Good Research Practices” at: http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf</i>	
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Future plans to strengthen research integrity will include the implementation of networking, open communication and information sharing, to heighten the principles of research integrity for future generations of researchers.</i>	
Gender equality	
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?	
Yes	
If Yes, please specify:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any gender has been involved in UNISA's GEP, a - The creation of family-friendly workspaces, such as a nursery and pink parking spaces for women and men with children - Employees can benefit from parental leave 	
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?	
<i>Involved</i>	
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?	
Yes	
Open access	
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)	
<i>Some time</i>	
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?	
<i>Newsletter Public Deliverable Posters produced in the context of the project</i>	
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)	
<i>Internal documents of the Consortium (such as meeting minutes, working documents) are not made public. Moreover, the Confidential Deliverables are of use only for the Consortium, as stated within the Grant Agreement.</i>	
Public engagement	

How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
14
Conferences:
2
Interviews:
0
Participatory events:
8
Surveys:
1
Social media:
2
Other:
4
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
Yes
If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:
<i>Exchanges with the local, national and international network have made it possible to improve the diffusion of gender in training, and has raised gender-awareness campaigns.</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
Yes
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>The project facilitated collaboration and knowledge exchange in the field of gender equality. Moreover, the university community shows a greater interest in gender-related events and are actively taking part in seminars and workshops promoted by the R&I PEERS team concerning gender-sensitive issues.</i>

RRI and GEP in your organization
Ethics
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?

<i>Much</i>
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution
<i>The discussion about gender is carried on not only by women A greater awareness of gender issues has led to a wider collaboration between scientific fields and humanities</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for an informed consent for images or personal data?
<i>Each time</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Each time</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among of staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Very frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Very beneficial</i>
For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
<i>The GEP involves people of different genders and identifies different skills and general interests to attribute responsibility for specific activities in the areas identified in the GEP.</i>
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
<i>No</i>
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
<i>No</i>
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
-
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
<i>The GEP is not available yet, but it will be made accessible as soon as the final version is completed</i>
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
<i>Yes</i>
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Very frequently</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Beneficial</i>

Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Strengthening the local network with industries and stakeholders, thanks to a bond the University has with the Salerno Female Committee of the Italian Industrial Federation and with the Councillor of Equal Opportunities of the Campania Region. Moreover, UNISA has a continuous exchange of best practices and ideas with the CUGs, on a regional and national level and other local stakeholders and associations (such as FIDAPA, the councillor for culture of the Municipality of Salerno, Salerno Literature festival). Step by step, UNISA is implementing the local network promoting gender-sensitive projects and events promoting them through the radio, magazines, television programs and blogs.</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Replicating initiatives implemented within the project on the local territory, such as the creation of pink parking spaces, and the installation of the red bench a symbol to combat violence against women</i>
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation
<i>The first Master on GE (Leadership, Gender Equality, Diversity Opportunity “LEGEnDO”) was approved on April 7, 2020, by the Department of Humanities Board of Professors. The teaching of “Women’s History and Gender Studies” is open to students of all disciplines and departments.</i>
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, please specify:
<i>This educational action has helped unhinge some rigid patterns that have traditionally defined relationships, choices and power relationships between women and men. It has revealed the need to build new relationship models in which both women and men must rethink themselves in terms of greater equality.</i>
If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)
<i>A fundraising campaign addressed to national enterprises, institutions and associations “ADOPT A TALENT, for gender equity” has been very successful in helping young talents. In fact, it will be launched again in the future to sustain financially the enrolment of students in Masters and postgraduate courses on Gender Equality.</i>

4.2 CYPRUS NEUROSCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY INSTITUTE (CNTI)

Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. CNTI is very familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. In particular, the selection of stakeholders invited to participate at the Mutual Learning Workshops was done taking into account the different RRI pillars, such as gender equality and engagement in a way that part of the group was comprised of both men and women who were not directly involved with the activities of the project. In addition, the development of the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) was the result of an engaging process involving the employees and the management structures. Finally, both the GEPs and the results from the Mutual Learning Workshops have been shared publicly online satisfying the provisions and demands for Open Access.

The Institute does not have a public ethical code, but the team involved in R&I-PEERS followed ethical practices and the staff members are very aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. In particular, the Institute uses the following practices: https://www.research-integrity.admin.cam.ac.uk/files/good_research_practice_guidelines_2018.pdf and https://www.sisnetwork.eu/media/sisnet/Policy_brief_Research_Integrity_SiSnet.pdf.

All the activities were carried out following the Ethical requirements, with the necessary informed consents, and the staff was aware and familiar with the procedures concerning the collection and processing of personal information.

Practices useful to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities can be provided by concrete examples within the Mutual Learning Workshops and presenting GEPs. This will enable to integrate this notion into the mindset of researchers.

The actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing the following impacts (evolutions) in terms of values: the gender equality is not treated as an issue which concerns only women, staff are more open to discuss gender equality issues now, staff approach gender issues in a more holistic way, staff now realize the women under-representation in the top management existence and the consequences of this situation.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, the CNTI focused on the creation of gender-balanced research teams, on a more balanced role of the coordination among males and females, flexible working hours, remote work. Furthermore, the Institute has also succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures. The activities in R&I-PEERS have facilitated the development of sincere communication and discussion around the GEP's measures and strategies, to this respect, both men and women had the chance to reflect together on the feasibility of the measures suggested to become beneficial for the majority of the employees.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, the Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute provided several project's outputs freely accessible: CNTI GEP, Mutual Learning Workshops' Reports, Trainings on gender dimension in research and barriers and boundaries of application of GE policies in Europe. The Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute has internal established Open Access practices to follow and made open accessible the defined GEP through the website.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, the Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute carried out 4 different public engagement activities involving very frequently people external to the organization and it was very beneficial reaching out them. The initiatives of the Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute were addressed to strengthening the network with local NGOs and SMEs. In particular, CNTI reached out people external to the organization through face to face meetings and joint events with other NGOs involved in gender equality.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, the Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute is not really active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy. Only few activities, focused on how to write scientific papers and research proposals, were planned in the organization’s GEP within workshops and webinars. This was beneficial as CNTI staff are now equipped with basic knowledge on how to integrate the gender aspects in research proposals.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Very Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<i>The selection of stakeholders to participate at the Mutual Learning Workshops took into account different RRI pillars, such as gender equality and engagement in a way that part of the group was comprised of both men and women who were not directly involved with the activities of the project. In addition, the development of the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) was the result of an engaging process involving the employees and the management structures in most of the organizations. Finally, both the GEPs and the results from the Mutual Learning Workshops have been shared publicly online satisfying the provisions and demands for Open Access.</i>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>No</i>	
If No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities’	
<i>Yes</i>	
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?	
<i>Very aware</i>	
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Scientific Integrity Principles and Best Practices: Recommendations from a Scientific Integrity Consortium https://www.research-integrity.admin.cam.ac.uk/files/good_research_practice_guidelines_2018.pdf https://www.sisnetwork.eu/media/sisnet/Policy_brief_Research_Integrity_SiSnet.pdf</i>	
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Where stakeholders interact with R&I-PEERS (Mutual Learning Workshops) as well as in the presentation of our GEPs to the staff of our institutions. Being involved in research activities does not necessarily make you familiar with research integrity. Therefore, providing concrete examples and best practices in research integrity is vital to integrate this notion into the mindset of the researchers.</i>	
Gender equality	
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?	
<i>Yes</i>	
If Yes, please specify:	

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gender-balanced research teams in our last project proposals 2. The role of the coordinator in our last project proposals has been assigned to a female 3. Flexible working hours 4. Remote work
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
<i>Yes</i>
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CNTI GEP 2. Mutual Learning Workshops' Reports 3. Trainings on the gender dimension in research and barriers and boundaries of application of GE policies in Europe.
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
<i>0</i>
Conferences:
<i>0</i>
Interviews:
<i>0</i>
Participatory events:
<i>0</i>
Surveys:
<i>0</i>
Social media:
<i>4</i>
Other:
<i>6</i>
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Slightly Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>I do not know</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>No</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Rarely</i>

If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
No

RRI and GEP in your organization
Ethics
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?
<i>Much</i>
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gender equality is not treated as an issue which concerns only women 2. Staff are more open to discuss gender equality issues now 3. Staff approach gender issues in a more holistic way 4. Staff now realize the existence and consequences of women under-representation in the top management
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for an informed consent for images or personal data?
<i>Each time</i>
If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered
<i>The staff at the organization are well familiarized with the ethical issues concerning the collection and processing of personal information and thus no difficulties were encountered.</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Frequently</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Very beneficial</i>
For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
<i>As described above, gender equality is not an issue concerning only women and bringing together men and women to discuss about our GEP facilitated the development of sincere communication and discussion around the GEP's measures and strategies. To this respect, both men and women had the chance to reflect together on the feasibility of the measures suggested to become beneficial for the majority of the employees.</i>
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
<i>Yes</i>

Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
Yes
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>Through our website.</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
-
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
-
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Very frequently</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
Very beneficial
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Local NGOs, SMEs</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Face to face meetings with the management of other NGOs Joint events with other NGOs involved in gender equality</i>
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation
<i>workshops and webinars</i>
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>The staff of the organization participated in the workshops and webinars on how to write scientific papers and research proposals.</i>
If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)
<i>It was beneficial in the sense that our staff are now equipped with basic knowledge on how to integrate the gender aspects in research proposals</i>

4.3 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)

CNR filled only the questionnaire of partners that are not piloting, because it is not implementing the GEP in the R&I-PEERS project.

CNR is very familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and, it has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. In particular, CNR took into account the five RRI pillars when: i) involving the different stakeholders during the participatory events and in the project activities, ii) promoting the gender balance as much as possible in the project, iii) considering and underlining the ethical issues connected with the activities planned and carried out.

CNR already has a public Ethical Code available at the link:

https://www.imamoter.cnr.it/pdf/Codice_Compportamento_CNR_2017.pdf

There is also a document that provides the guidelines for the research integrity and, it is available at:

https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/doc_istituzionali/linee-guida-integrita-nella-ricerca-cnr-commissione_etica.pdf?v=4

The team involved in R&I-PEERS is very aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules have been followed in:

- Research protocols that take into account of and, that are sensitive to relevant differences in age, gender, culture, religion, ethnic origin and social class.
- Ensure access to data possibly following an open approach.
- Transparency about how to access or make use of data and research materials.
- Acknowledgement of data as legitimate and citable products of research.
- Working for ensuring that any contracts or agreements relating to research outputs include equitable and fair provision for the management of their use, ownership, and/or their protection under intellectual property rights.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, an effort has been done to approximate as much as possible a gender balance in the project staff. Furthermore, the CNR also succeeded in reaching external people when promoting equal participation and people and including gender perspective. People enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, CNR provided the project's outputs freely accessible, in particular: shared public deliverables, and the poster produced are made open (once approved by PO). Only private documents, such as the minutes of the project are not public.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, CNR carried out 32 different public engagement activities involving frequently people external to the organization that considered beneficial their participation.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, CNR organises many activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy.

For example, Sveva Avveduto organised the Ada Lovelace Day, with the contribution of Ilaria Di Tullio, Fabio Fornasari and Lucio Pisacane from CNR-IRPPS and the contribution of Guido Righini from CNR-IC, and Paola Verrucchi from CNR-ISC. The Ada Lovelace Day is the international event that every year on the second Tuesday of October promotes and collects initiatives from all countries of the world for the promotion of the study of scientific subjects by girls and the elimination of prejudices and gender stereotypes as well as access barriers and career progression for women.

The ViVa project (PROJECT OF MONITORING, EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS FOR PREVENTION AND CONTRAST INTERVENTION AGAINST VIOLENCE ON WOMEN), coordinated by Maura Misiti, organized the training courses, carried out in collaboration with Crasform (<https://crasform2.wixsite.com/crasform>).

These courses took place from October 2018 to April 2019 for a total of 12 days. The contents proposed by teachers, scholars and scholars, stakeholders, activists and activists and representatives of local,

national and international institutions were divided into five training modules on:1: Violence against women2: Basic introductory concepts3: Tools against gender violence4: The institutional response system to gender-based violence5: The territorial response system to gender violence6: Adoption of a gender perspective in the research activities of the ViVa project7: Testimonials and evaluation. The speakers for courses were: Serena Battilomo, Paola Bianchi, Franca Bimbi, Grazia Biondi, Stefano Ciccone, Tiziana dal Pra, Antonella Faieta, Valentina Falcone, Patrizia Farina, Silvia Garambois, Sonia Lama, Simona Lanzoni, Andrea Mazzeo Maura Misiti, Giuseppina Muratore, Lella Palladino, Antonella Petricone, Michele Poli, Maria Spitti, Virginia Peschiera, Serenella Pignotti, Vittoria Tola, Maria Pia Vigilante. The CNR Communications Office periodically organises meetings of science education that are registered and shared on YouTube. They are available at:
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCK9RXmjvOiVe_eUPkIBVJ6w

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Very Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
Involving in the project activities the different stakeholders during the participatory events, taking into account of the gender balance as much as possible in the project, considering and underlining the ethical issues connected with the activities carried out.	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>Yes</i>	
If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.	
Ethical code: https://www.imamoter.cnr.it/pdf/Codice_Compportamento_CNR_2017.pdf there is also a document that provides the guidelines for the research integrity and, it is available at: https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/doc_istituzionali/linee-guida-integrita-nella-ricerca-cnr-commissione_etica.pdf?v=4 .	
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?	
<i>Very aware</i>	
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
All principles are in general followed. In general, we always consider: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research protocols that take into account of and, that are sensitive to relevant differences in age, gender, culture, religion, ethnic origin and social class. • Ensure access to data possibly following an open approach. • Transparency about how to access or make use of data and research materials. • Acknowledgment of data as legitimate and citable products of research. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working for ensuring that any contracts or agreements relating to research outputs include equitable and fair provision for the management of their use, ownership, and/or their protection under intellectual property rights.
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
All principle should be followed
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
An effort has been asked to have a gender balance in the project staff.
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
Yes
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Some time</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
Public deliverables, the poster produced are made open (once approved)
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
Only private documents, such as the minutes of the project are not public.
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
-
Conferences:
1
Interviews:
-
Participatory events:
1
Surveys:
-
Social media:
-
Other:
30 (<i>sharing news on social media or in other events</i>)
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
No

Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
Yes
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
Some time
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS ?
-
If Yes, Please, specify
<p>CNR and IRPPS organise events on science education related to many disciplines and topics. Some of these activities are also related to Gender equality.</p> <p>For example, Sveva Avveduto organised the Ada Lovelace Day, with the contribution of Ilaria Di Tullio, Fabio Fornasari and Lucio Pisacane from CNR-IRPPS and the contribution of Guido Righini from CNR-IC, and Paola Verrucchi from CNR-ISC. The Ada Lovelace Day is the international event that every year on the second Tuesday of October promotes and collects initiatives from all countries of the world for the promotion of the study of scientific subjects by girls and the elimination of prejudices and gender stereotypes as well as access barriers and career progression for women.</p> <p>The ViVa project (PROJECT OF MONITORING, EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS FOR PREVENTION AND CONTRAST INTERVENTION AGAINST VIOLENCE ON WOMEN), coordinated by Maura Misiti, organized the training courses, carried out in collaboration with Crasform (https://crasform2.wixsite.com/crasform). These courses took place from October 2018 to April 2019 for a total of 12 days. The contents proposed by teachers, scholars and scholars, stakeholders, activists and activists and representatives of local, national and international institutions were divided into five training modules on:1: Violence against women2: Basic introductory concepts3: Tools against gender violence4: The institutional response system to gender-based violence5: The territorial response system to gender violence6: Adoption of a gender perspective in the research activities of the ViVa project7: Testimonials and evaluation. The speakers for courses were: Serena Battilomo, Paola Bianchi, Franca Bimbi, Grazia Biondi, Stefano Ciccone, Tiziana dal Pra, Antonella Faieta, Valentina Falcone, Patrizia Farina, Silvia Garambois, Sonia Lama, Simona Lanzoni, Andrea Mazzeo Maura Misiti, Giuseppina Muratore, Lella Palladino, Antonella Petricone, Michele Poli, Maria Spitti, Virginia Peschiera, Serenella Pignotti, Vittoria Tola, Maria Pia Vigilante.</p> <p>The CNR Communications Office periodically organises meetings of science education that are registered and shared on YouTube. They are available at: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCK9RXmjvOiVe_eUPkIBVJ6w</p>

4.4 ASSOCIAZIONE INDUSTRIALI DELLA PROVINCIA DI SALERNO (AISAI)

AISAI filled only the questionnaire of partners that are not piloting, because it is not implementing the GEP in the R&I-PEERS project. AISAI is familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has very frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. In particular, at AISAI, the five RRI pillars were generally considered: during the workshop, conferences and trainings; in engaging various stakeholders and different people not included in the organisations' staff; in following the rules of the Ethical Code.

AISAI already has a public Ethical Code available at link: <https://www.confindustria.sa.it/codice-etico>. "Associazione industriali della provincial di Salerno" organises opportunities for dialogues and exchange

of opinions with all the components of the community of reference and of the territory, to build system innovations to gather the different demands and interests, to contribute to the common good through sustainable development models. Associated entrepreneurs must behave in full consistency with the values, principles and commitments stated in the Ethical Code and associative values, ensure fair and safe working conditions for their employees and collaborators, respectful of dignity, equal opportunities and free from any form of discrimination or exploitation, capable of promoting human and professional development in any context, ethical and transparent behaviour based on responsibility, integrity, fairness, loyalty, fairness and free market. The team involved in R&I-PEERS is aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules have been taken in associative relationships and towards Stakeholders, according to ethical and transparent behaviours, based on integrity, fairness, loyalty, fairness, impartiality, independence and autonomy of judgment, absence of conflicts of interest. AISAI key to action is based on education to difference, which means training people capable of developing their personal abilities outside of stereotypes, beyond prejudices and gender limits. In the R&I-PEERS activities AISAI will be always focused on improving a model of "good practice" from a gender equality perspective pushing the research integrity principles.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, AISAI already implemented a GEP focused on building a gender-balanced team with people having different and transversals skills that can satisfy practical rational aspect of men and the emotional aspect closer to women, to work by innovative way. AISAI, within the R&I-PEERS activities, adopts practices to promote the team to organise the activities together, balancing the different approaches to operate in a climate where meritocracy and skills are privileged over gender. Furthermore, AISAI has also succeeded in reaching external people for promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, AISAI provided the project’s outputs freely accessible: Upgrading project, Articles, Videos, media social network, Dissemination of activities during workshop and trainings.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, AISAI carried out 22 different public engagement activities involving frequently people external to the organization. These activities were considered satisfying, even if they did not produce a change in the activities or practices during the project.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, AISAI is really active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy also with the contribution of the R&I-PEERS project, by organizing:

- Training course on finance organized by AISAI in collaboration with Jobiz formazione/MIP management school.
- Training course on "DESIGN THINKING FOR BUSINESS" organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school,
- Training course on "Leadership e gestione del team di innovazione" (Leadership and management of the team on innovation) organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school
- Training course on "Business Model Innovation" organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization
General issues about RRI
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?
<i>Familiar</i>
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?

<i>Very frequently</i>
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>During the workshop, conferences and training;</i> - <i>Engaging various stakeholders and different people not included in the organisations' staff;</i> - <i>Following Ethical Code.</i>
Ethics
Has your organization an Ethical code
Yes
If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.
<p><i>Link: https://www.confindustria.sa.it/codice-etico</i></p> <p><i>Confindustria Salerno, dialogues and compares itself with all the components of the community of reference and the territory, to build system innovations that know how to gather the different demands and interests, to contribute to the common good through sustainable development models.</i></p> <p><i>associated entrepreneurs must behave in full consistency with the values, principles and commitments stated in the Code of Ethics and associative values, ensure fair and safe working conditions for their employees and collaborators, respectful of dignity, equal opportunities and free from any form of discrimination or exploitation, capable of promoting human and professional development</i></p> <p><i>- in any context, ethical and transparent behaviour based on responsibility, integrity, fairness, loyalty, fairness and free market</i></p>
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?
<i>Aware</i>
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Confindustria Salerno directs its action, both in associative relationships and towards Stakeholders, according to ethical and transparent behaviours, based on integrity, fairness, loyalty, fairness, impartiality, independence and autonomy of judgment, absence of conflicts of interest</i>
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Our key to action is based on education to difference, which means training people capable of developing their personal abilities outside of stereotypes, beyond prejudices and gender limits. In the R&I-PEERS activities we will be always focused on improving a model of "good practice" from a gender equality perspective.</i>
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>We build a gender-balanced team whit people we have different and transversals skills that can satisfy practical rational aspect of men and the emotional aspect closer to women, to work by innovative way. We promote the team to organise the activities together, balancing the different approaches to operate in a climate where meritocracy and skills are privileged over gender.</i>
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Moderately involved</i>

In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
<i>Yes</i>
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Very Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<i>Upgrading project Articles, Videos, media social network Dissemination of activities during workshop, training</i>
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
<i>-</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
<i>10</i>
Conferences:
<i>3</i>
Interviews:
<i>5</i>
Participatory events:
<i>0</i>
Surveys:
<i>1</i>
Social media:
<i>3</i>
Other:
<i>0</i>
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>No</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>Yes</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, Please, specify

Training course on finance organized by AISAI in collaboration with Jobiz formazione/MIP management school.
Training course on "DESIGN THINKING FOR BUSINESS" organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school,
Training course on "Leadership e gestione del team di innovazione" organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school
Training course on "Business Model Innovation" organized by AISAI in collaboration with MIP management school

4.5 ASOCIACION - CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN NANOCIENCIAS (CIC NANO GUNE)

CIC nanoGUNE is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. This organisation is very familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities, in particular for:

- Public engagement: In the creation and activity of the Gender Equality Committee (an example of public engagement)
- Science-education: In the outreach activities carried out (Celebration of the International Day of Women in Science for the promotion of women and girls in science)
- Gender equality: in the constitution of the Gender Equality Committee
- Open science: there are no related publications so far
- Ethics: all the actions comply with ethics requirements which also follows CIC nanoGUNE "Ethical code".

CIC nanoGUNE has a public ethical code and the team involved in R&I-PEERS is very aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical code is available at: <https://www.nanogune.eu/es/corporate-compliance>. Ethics has been followed using practices to promote Collaborative work, the growth of the awareness of the importance of data management and data protection, mentoring and supervision, supporting developing ideas. CIC nanoGUNE moreover, suggests introducing in R&I-PEERS useful Initiatives and practice that promote interactive and collaborative work (online) on documents with associated discussion, so that opinions can be taken into account for the R&I-PEERS' activities.

The actions planned and implemented within the GEP need more time to be evaluated the impact on ethics: at the moment it is difficult to know if the actions planned and implemented will inspire people. To really know it, we would have to measure the impact of the actions on people's mindsets. Generally speaking, the R&I-PEERS team of CIC nanoGUNE have not detected changes in the atmosphere. Nevertheless, the discussion is now wider including both females and males.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, the Institute focused on building gender-balance project teams, implementing conciliation measures in less than one year. Furthermore, CIC nanoGUNE has partially succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures. The activities in R&I-PEERS have stimulated equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members and this was very beneficial for the definition of GEP per se.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, CIC nanoGUNE provided the project's outputs freely accessible very frequently, and in particular, are open the leaflets of WinS (Celebration of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science). CIC nanoGUNE has internal established Open Access practices to follow and, made open accessible the defined GEP through the intranet.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, CIC nanoGUNE did not organize formally events of public engagement. The initiatives of CIC nanoGUNE were addressed to establish informal contacts with to research centres nearby for exchanging information among peers.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, CIC nanoGUNE is planned to organise very frequently activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy.

Open days with workshops, webinars, talks where gender balance by the speaker was included in the GEP. One activity was implemented: the yearly “Women and Girls in Science Week”. It focused on the promotion of women and girls in science.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Very familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<p><i>Public engagement: In the creation and activity of the Gender Equality Committee (an example of public engagement)</i></p> <p><i>Science-education: In the outreach activities carried out (Celebration of the International Day of Women in Science for the promotion of women and girls in science)</i></p> <p><i>Gender equality: in the constitution of the Gender Equality Committee</i></p> <p><i>Open science: there are no related publications so far</i></p> <p><i>Ethics: all the actions comply with ethics requirements which also follows nanoGUNE “Ethical code”</i></p>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>Yes</i>	
if Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.	
<p><i>https://www.nanogune.eu/es/corporate-compliance</i></p> <p><i>All, as no illegal action has been carried out related to the actions per se and the data protection regulation.</i></p>	
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?	
<i>Very aware</i>	
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Collaborative work, rising awareness of the importance of data management and data protection, mentoring and supervision, supporting developing ideas...</i>	
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	

<i>Interactive and collaborative work (online) on documents with associated discussion, so that opinions can be considered in line.</i>
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>Building gender-balance project teams, implementing conciliation measures in less than a year</i>
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Slightly Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
Yes
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<i>The leaflets of WinS (Celebration of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science)</i>
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
<i>We did not produce others.</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
<i>0</i>
Conferences:
<i>0</i>
Interviews:
<i>0</i>
Participatory events:
<i>0</i>
Surveys:
<i>0</i>
Social media:
<i>0</i>
Other:
<i>0</i>
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
-
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
-
If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:
-

Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>Yes</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, please specify:
<i>WinS (International day for the promotion of women and girls in science)</i>

RRI and GEP in your organization
Ethics
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?
<i>Neutral</i>
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution
<i>In general, we cannot know if the actions planned and implemented will inspire people. To really know it, we would have to measure the impact of the actions on people's mindsets.</i>
<i>On a different note, we have not detected any change in the atmosphere. Nevertheless, the discussion is now wider including both females and males.</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?
<i>Each time</i>
If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered
<i>When we carry out the extensive survey, we asked for an informed consent form to be accepted. We did not find any difficulties</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Each time</i>
Please, explain what are the difficulties in adopting a responsible process (if any)
<i>Nothing to report</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Very frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Very beneficial</i>

For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
<i>It was very beneficial for the definition of all the aspects of the GEP, per se.</i>
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
Yes
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
Yes
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>In the intranet of the organisation</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
-
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
-
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Beneficial</i>
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Informally, to research centres nearby</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Exchange of information amongst peers is always beneficial, as we face similar problems.</i>
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Very frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation
<i>Open days with workshops, webinars, talks where gender balance by the speaker is desired...</i>
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>The yearly “Women and Girls in Science Week” for the promotion of women and girls in science. About the gender dimension in research introduction, people claimed it does not apply to their research but to bio-related projects.</i>

<p>If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)</p>
<p><i>To inspire new generations of women to pursue a scientific career, as well as raising awareness on equality</i></p> <p><i>The concept of considering the gender dimension in research was new to most of the people so created awareness</i></p>

4.6 GALILEE RESEARCH INSTITUTE LTD (MIGAL)

MIGAL is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. This organisation is familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has very frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities, in particular for:

- Public engagement: R&I-PEERS Project started with a survey to understand what the gender state in the different organisations. This was the starting point and it's included the employees that were involved and were informed of the project and its ideas.
- Open access: We have promoted a number of measures to create Open access: 1. Project paper 2. Website 3. The platform 4. Deliverables documents and activities (workshops...)
- Promoting formal and informal science education: MIGAL occasionally performs informal workshops, enrichment workshops. The goal is awarding skills and personal empowerment researchers, networking and exposure to new areas.

MIGAL does not have a public ethical code, it has a suitable committee to submit an application for an experimental protocol in accordance with the Israeli law for any ethical issue. The team involved in R&I-PEERS is aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules related to the integrity of research are taken into account. In fact, senior researchers, research leaders and supervisor mentor their team members and offer specific guidance and training to properly develop, design and structure their research activity at all departments at MIGAL. We have given a unique opportunity for young researchers to advance their ideas with deliberate guidance.

- MIGALs researchers take into account the state-of-the-art in developing research ideas.
 - Researchers report their results in a way that is compatible with the standards of the discipline.
- MIGAL followed a responsible process of communication and information, in fact, pictures were taken with the knowledge of the participants and selected as less personal or embarrassing for the participants. MIGAL is following both the national laws and GDPR, Indeed MIGAL's main problem was the gap between Israeli and European GDPR privacy law when built the project platform. The impact produced by the GEP activities is quite neutral at the moment.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, the MIGAL focused on building a gender-balanced team (The main employees of the project are one man and one woman) for the R&I-PEERS project and, MIGAL organises the work according to a family-friendly workspace, etc. this is quite friendly at MIGAL. Furthermore, the MIGAL has also succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures. The activities in R&I-PEERS have facilitated the involvement and stimulated equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, MIGAL provided the project's outputs freely accessible: An article in the project newsletter, few publications at a local magazine, few publications at MIGAL's Facebook and MIGAL's site. MIGAL publishes the required documents on the platform when approved for publication. MIGAL has established Open Access practices to follow and, at the moment, made some of the GEP activities public and, then their contents accessible by conducting a workshop and inviting employees to hear about equality lectures, an invitation to participate in a sticker campaign within the organization to promote the gender equality awareness.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, MIGAL carried out 4 different public engagement activities involving sometimes people external to the organization that considered Beneficial their participation. The initiatives of MIGAL were addressed to family members of colleges from MIGAL by personal talks and I used the media to reach more people from the area (Facebook, radio and local newspapers). MIGAL is implementing a strategy for influencing the public opinion, in fact, the benefit in reaching out to people external to the organisation creates the effect of public discourse. and that can bring about a change of public opinion and a rolling influence.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, MIGAL, in general, is not very active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy.

However, MIGAL is sometimes active for science education in R&I-PEERS GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science with workshops and seminars. This was beneficial for managing the upgrade and scale up the activity of women researchers in submitting for funding and scientific papers. This was beneficial to increase the sensitivity of the importance of gender dimension in science and research.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Very frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<p><i>Public engagement: R&I-PEERS Project started with a survey to understand what the gender state in the different organisations. This was the starting point and it's included the employees that were involved and were informed of the project and its ideas.</i></p> <p><i>Open access: We have promoted a number of measures to create Open access.</i></p> <p><i>1. Project paper 2. Website 3. The platform 4. Deliverables documents and activities (workshops...)</i></p> <p><i>Promote formal and informal science education: MIGAL occasionally performs informal workshops, enrichment workshops. The goal is awarding skills and personal empowerment researchers, networking and exposure to new areas.</i></p>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>No</i>	
If No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities'	
<p><i>Yes, MIGAL is obligated like any Israeli institution of Israeli law and every ethical issue has a suitable committee to submit an application for an experimental protocol. This is done through the Helsinki committees in hospitals under the Ministry of Health regulations for</i></p>	

<i>experiments involving humans. Also, the Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee for Experiments.</i>
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?
<i>Aware</i>
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Senior researchers, research leaders and supervisor mentor their team members and offer specific guidance and training to properly develop, design and structure their research activity at all departments at MIGAL. We have given a unique opportunity for young researchers to advance their ideas with deliberate guidance.</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>MIGALs researchers take into account the state-of-the-art in developing research ideas.</i> • <i>Researchers report their results in a way that is compatible with the standards of the discipline.</i>
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>It may be interesting to make a fundamental comparison between the partners in terms of the principles used in the research.</i>
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
<i>Yes</i>
<i>If Yes, please specify:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Build a project gender-balanced team (The main employees of the project are one man and one woman).</i> • <i>organise the work according to a family-friendly workspace, etc. this is quite friendly at MIGAL.</i>
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Slightly involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
<i>Yes</i>
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<i>An article in the project newsletter, few publications at a local magazine, few publications at MIGALs Facebook and MIGALs site. We publish the required documents on the platform when approved for publication</i>
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
<i>We did not publish document of the project that didn't get PO approval.</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
<i>1</i>
Conferences:
<i>1</i>

Interviews:
1
Participatory events:
0
Surveys:
0
Social media:
1
Other:
0
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Slightly satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>No</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>Yes</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Rarely</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
<i>No</i>

RRI and GEP in your organization	
Ethics	
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?	
<i>Neutral</i>	
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution	
<i>Neutral; because the main plan to take the project into a specific goal was not carried out, on the other hand, the participants had tools to help them improve and the whole project was discussed by a variety of MIGAL employees.</i>	
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered	
<i>Pictures were taken with the knowledge of the participants. However, no permission was specifically obtained for every picture. We conducted self-esteem and endeavoured to take the photos as less personal or embarrassing for the participants. Mainly the images that were later used to publish the project.</i>	

When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Frequently</i>
Please, explain what are the difficulties in adopting a responsible process (if any)
<i>MIGAL's main problem was the gap between Israeli and European GDPR privacy law when we built the project platform; we were unaware that there was no compliance.</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Neutral</i>
For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
-
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
<i>Yes</i>
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>We made it some of the activities accessible by conducting a workshop and invite employees to hear about equality lectures, an invitation to participate in a sticker campaign within the organization to promote the equality awareness.</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
-
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
-
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Beneficial</i>
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>I reached to family members of colleges from MIGAL by personal talks and I used the media to reach more people from the area (Facebook, radio and local newspapers)</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>The benefit in reaching out to people external to the organisation creates the effect of public discourse. and that can bring about a change of public opinion and a rolling influence.</i>

Science Education	
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?	
<i>Some time</i>	
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation	
<i>Workshops, seminars</i>	
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?	
Yes	
If Yes, please specify:	
<i>By doing GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science we manage to upgrade and scale up the activity of women researcher in submitting for funding and scientific papers</i>	
If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)	
<i>To be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research,</i>	

4.7 DIGITAL LEADERSHIP INSTITUTE (DLI)

DLI filled in only the questionnaire of partners that are not piloting, because it is not implementing the GEP in the R&I-PEERS project. DLI is moderately familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. In particular, at DLI the five RRI pillars were generally considered in: In organizing events, engaging stakeholders, promoting ethics in research and industry, etc.. DLI does not have a public Ethical Code, however, the DLI staff followed and follows ethical practices during the project activities. In fact, the team involved in R&I-PEERS is very aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research and DLI researchers and consultants promote a high level of integrity in their work through fact- and source-checking, and practicing other ethics standards like honesty in reporting, journalism, etc.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, DLI already has a gender equality plan concerning Family-friendly work scheduling, work-from-home, family-friendly workspace, etc.. Furthermore, DLI also has succeeded in reaching external people when promoting equal participation and, people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, DLI as the project partner responsible for dissemination made public information available from the project as much as possible.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, DLI carried out 313 different public engagement activities involving frequently people external to the organization that considered beneficial their participation. In particular, DLI established collaboration with other EU projects with similar missions. It has succeeded in broadening the impact of engagement beyond what was originally planned, e.g. the #Gearing Leaders Women in Leadership campaign of the Sisters Project, which includes partners of R&I-PEERS and other organisations as well.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, DLI is active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy. DLI regularly carry out science

literacy programs, especially in computer science for communities that are persistently excluded from such activities, especially communities of girls and women, including from the most vulnerable backgrounds.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Neutral</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<i>In organizing events, engaging stakeholders, promoting ethics in research and industry, etc</i>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>No</i>	
If No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities?	
<i>Yes</i>	
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?	
<i>Very aware</i>	
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>We do not generally carry out research as an organization, especially in the current project, but our individual researchers and consultants promote a high level of integrity in their work through fact- and source-checking, and practicing other ethics standards like honesty in reporting, journalism, etc.</i>	
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?	
<i>Publishing, gaining commitment to and reporting on research integrity principles in the project.</i>	
Gender equality	
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?	
<i>Yes</i>	
If Yes, please specify:	
<i>Family-friendly work schedules. work-from-home, family-friendly workspace, etc.</i>	
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?	
<i>Strongly involved</i>	
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?	
<i>Yes</i>	
Open access	
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)	
<i>Very Frequently</i>	
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?	
<i>All, as the project partner responsible for dissemination we made public all information available from the project that was possible.</i>	

Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
-
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
3
Conferences:
4
Interviews:
0
Participatory events:
6
Surveys:
0
Social media:
300
Other:
0
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Very satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
Yes
If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:
<i>Collaboration with other EU projects with similar missions has succeeded in broadening the impact of engagement beyond what was originally planned, e.g. the #Gearing Leaders Women in Leadership campaign of the Sisters Projects, which includes partners of R&I PEERS and other organisations as well.</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
Yes
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Very frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
Yes
If Yes, Please, specify
<i>We regularly carry out science literacy programs, especially computer science, for communities that are persistently excluded from such activities, especially communities of girls and women, including from the most vulnerable backgrounds.</i>

4.8 ZNANSTVENORAZISKOVALNI CENTER SLOVENSKE AKADEMIJE ZNANOSTI IN UMETNOSTI (ZRC SAZU)

ZRC SAZU is a pilot organisation in the R&I-PEERS project. This organisation is familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has very frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. ZRC SAZU participates as a partner in the ongoing Horizon 2020 project GRACE (Grounding RRI Actions to Achieve Institutional Changes in European Research Funding and Performing Organisations, 2020-2021). In particular, at ZRC SAZU, the five RRI pillars are usually considered when performing research and organizational tasks; in the framework of R&I-PEERS project, ZRC SAZU also considered them in various project activities and implementation of the GEP. More concretely:

- In conducting surveys for the project needs and in conceptualizing strategies for GEP, ZRC SAZU considered ethic guidelines of the project, as well as those specific for certain academic fields (e.g. the Code of ethics of the American Anthropological Association (<https://www.americananthro.org/LearnAndTeach/Content.aspx?ItemNumber=22869&navItemNumber=652>) for interviews and ethnographic research).
- ZRC SAZU makes sure that all the activities are transparently communicated to the employees and the wider audience; all project-related publications are freely accessible and widely distributed.
- From the very beginning, ZRC SAZU designed project activities to include stakeholders (employees and those outside the organization) and to interconnect as many and as diverse employees of ZRC SAZU as possible, insisting on the importance of horizontal connecting and cooperation and on networking with similar groups in Slovenia.
- From the beginning, the project activities were framed as a public engagement, principally through their integration and promotion within two bodies: The Commission for equal opportunities in Science in Slovenia and informal group ALT+G – community of practice formed in the framework of the sister project ACT.
- In the project related activities organized, ZRC SAZU tried to secure the diversity of participants (gender, age, ethnicity, career stage).

ZRC SAZU does not have a public ethical code but it is in the process for adopting its own, as an activity of the GRACE project. The team involved in R&I-PEERS is very aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules have been taken in securing an appropriate research environment for involved researchers; the work is done collaboratively and, data are appropriately managed and stored. Contribution of all team members is acknowledged; all involved researchers are informed about all the steps and the activities in the project. Furthermore, the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are contributing to more frequent discussions among employees on gender equality and other equal opportunity issues. These activities have made many employees, particularly on decision making positions, more aware of the importance of gender equality and inclusiveness. Through GEP related activities many employees, regardless of gender, connected and joined initiatives and started exchanging experiences and information. ZRC SAZU follows each time a responsible process of communication and information and asks for informed consent for images and/or personal data and the organized activities are documented with the informed consent of the participants. Ethic requirements were followed for all the surveys and questionnaires.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, the ZRC SAZU's GEP focuses on promoting the excellence of female researchers and the increasing possibility of teleworking and flexible working hours. Furthermore, ZRC SAZU has also succeeded in reaching external stakeholders in promoting equal participation and encouraging diversity regarding ethnicity, career stage, gender, family situation, etc.. The activities of the GEP in R&I-PEERS frequently stimulated equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members; they were very beneficial. In fact, the diversity of employees involved in the implementation of GEP measures – not only regarding gender but also age, ethnicity, career stage, work

position etc. enabled considering multiple perspectives that it was not always easy to anticipate before the GEP actions implementation.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, ZRC SAZU provided the project’s outputs freely accessible. In particular, are open: deliverables approved by the Project Officer, reports on specific activities (that are published and made public), the GEP text (available in the website: https://ikss.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/gep_zrc_sazu_slofinal-javno.pdf), newsletters and information on ongoing activities are published on the website <https://spolinznanoz.zrc-sazu.si/>. Some of the reports ZRC SAZU created in the process of GEP implementation concerned internal practices are not public; but are public summaries with the most relevant findings. Open access is regulated by requirements set by the Slovenian research Agency (ARRS) as well as organization’s own protocols.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, ZRC SAZU carried out 10 different public engagement activities involving very frequently people external to the organization and they were very satisfying. Reaching external stakeholders with these activities was considered beneficial. These initiatives aimed at intersecting ZRC SAZU’s activities with similar activities or initiatives in other research institutions in Slovenia. In the framework of the sister project ACT, in which ZRC SAZU also participates, other interested researchers are involved in discussions and experience exchange related to the implementation of GEP measures (e.g. in March, a workshop was organized to discuss the use of the gender-sensitive language. Researchers and administrative staff from other Slovenian RPOs have also been invited); ZRC SAZU distributes its bi-monthly newsletter to a wide variety of stakeholders. ZRC SAZU also works with the Commission for Equal Opportunity in Science to share information on the GEP implementation and to discuss various issues related to it. It was beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation as this stimulated an exchange of information and experiences, the co-organizing of events and discussions. Moreover, many of the activities closely related to the GEP implementation have been conducted in the framework of the community of practice that includes several Slovenian RPOs, established within the sister project ACT. Finally, it is important to consider that some institutional changes are easier to implement if it is possible to show that other RPOs are going in the same direction.

Regarding the pillar of Science education, ZRC SAZU is really active and frequently it organizes activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy also with the contribution of the R&I-PEERS project. In particular, R&I-PEERS project team organised and will keep organising workshops on including gender perspective into research; ZRC offers a series of research workshops for children in summer; gender aspects are also considered in presenting research results to broad audiences; as part of GEP, ZRC SAZU is preparing a book presenting female researchers from various fields in South-eastern Europe. The ZRC SAZU community (internal and external) shows a great interest in gender equality related events and these activities are beneficial as they help raising awareness on the importance of gender equality and inclusiveness in science and education practices. They also make science educators aware and sensitives to gender issues and their relevance.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Very Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	

<p><i>At ZRC SAZU, the five RRI pillars are generally considered in performing research and organizational tasks; in the framework of R&I-PEERS project, we also considered them in various project activities and in implementation of the GEP. More concretely:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>In conducting surveys for the project needs and in conceptualizing strategies for GEP, we considered ethic guidelines of the project, as well as those specific for certain academic fields (e.g. the Code of ethics of the American Anthropological Association (https://www.americananthro.org/LearnAndTeach/Content.aspx?ItemNumber=22869&navItemNumber=652) for interviews and ethnographic research).</i> - <i>We make sure that all the activities are transparently communicated to the employees and the wider audience; all project-related publications are freely accessible and widely distributed.</i> - <i>From the very beginning, we designed project activities to include stakeholders (employees and those outside the organization) and to interconnect as many and as diverse employees of ZRC SAZU as possible, insisting on the importance of horizontal connecting and cooperation and on networking with similar groups in Slovenia.</i> - <i>From the beginning, the project activities were framed as public engagement, principally through their integration and promotion within two bodies: The Commission for equal opportunities in Science in Slovenia and informal group ALT+G – community of practice formed in the framework of the sister project ACT.</i> - <i>In the project related activities organized, we tried to secure the diversity of participants (gender, age, ethnicity, career stage).</i>
Ethics
Has your organization an Ethical code
<i>No</i>
If No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities?
<i>Yes, ZRC SAZU is in the process of adopting its Ethical code.</i>
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?
<i>Very aware</i>
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>We secure an appropriate research environment for involved researchers; the work is done in a collaborative way and data are appropriately managed and stored. Contribution of all team members is acknowledged; all involved researchers are informed about all the steps and activities in the project.</i>
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Same of the previous answer</i>
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, please specify:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>promoting the excellence of female researchers</i> - <i>increasing the possibility of telework and flexible working hours</i>
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?

Yes
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Very Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - deliverables approved by PO has been made public - reports on specific activities are published and made public - GEP text is made public - newsletters and information on ongoing activities is published on the website https://spoliznanost.zrc-sazu.si/
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
<i>Some of the reports we created in the process of GEP implementation concerned internal practices; we did not make them public, but we made public a summary with the most relevant findings.</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
3
Conferences:
1
Interviews:
2
Participatory events:
3
Surveys:
1
Social media:
-
Other:
-
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?
<i>Very Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>No</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
Yes
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
Yes
If Yes, Please, specify

- *workshops on including gender into science research*
- *raising general public knowledge on female scientists from the past (preparation of the monograph)*

RRI and GEP in your organization	
Ethics	
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?	
<i>Very Much</i>	
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution	
<i>GEP related activities at ZRC SAZU contribute to more frequent discussions on gender equality and other equal opportunity issues; these activities have made many employees, particularly on decision making positions, more aware of the importance of GE and inclusiveness. Through GEP related activities many employees, regardless of gender, connected and joined initiatives and started exchanging experiences and information.</i>	
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?	
<i>Each time</i>	
If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered	
<i>All the organized activities are documented with the informed consent of the participants. Ethic requirements were also followed for all the surveys and questionnaires. No specific difficulties occurred.</i>	
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?	
<i>Each time</i>	
Please, explain what are the difficulties in adopting a responsible process (if any)	
<i>There were no difficulties.</i>	
Gender equality	
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among of staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?	
<i>Very beneficial</i>	
For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.	
<i>Diversity of employees involved in the implementation of GEP measures – not only regarding gender but also age, ethnicity, career stage, work position etc. enabled considering multiple perspectives that we were not always able to anticipate before implementation</i>	
Open access	
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow	

Yes
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
Yes
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>It is available on the website of our institute: https://ikss.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/gep_zrc_sazu_slofinal-javno.pdf</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
-
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
-
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Very frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Beneficial</i>
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>We put a lot of effort to intersect our activities with similar activities or initiatives in other research institutions in Slovenia. In the framework of the sister project ACT, in which we also participate, we involve other interested researchers in discussions and experience exchange related to the implementation of GEP measures (e.g. in March, we organized a workshop on the use of the gender-sensitive language and invited researchers and administrative staff from other Slovenian RPOs); we distribute our bi-monthly newsletter to a wide variety of stakeholders. We also use the Commission for Equal Opportunity in Science to share information on our GEP implementation and discuss various issues related to it.</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>We all benefit from the exchange of information and experiences, from co-organizing events and discussions; lots of activities closely related to GEP implementation are conducted in the framework of the community of practice that includes several Slovenian RPOs, established within the sister project ACT. Some institutional changes are easier to implement if we can show that other RPOs are going in the same direction.</i>
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation
<i>We organize workshops on including gender perspective into research; ZRC SAZU organizes a series of research workshops for the summer; gender aspects are also considered in presenting research results to broad audiences; as part of GEP, we are preparing a book presenting female researchers from various fields in South-eastern Europe</i>

Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
<i>These activities helped raising awareness of the importance of gender equality and inclusiveness in science education practices and make the general climate in the organization more reflective of these issues.</i>
If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)
<i>These activities help raising awareness of the importance of gender equality and inclusiveness in science education practices. They also make science educators aware and sensitives to gender issues and their relevance.</i>

4.9 AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA PROMOTION DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (ANPRT)

ANPRT is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. It is familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and has frequently taken into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities. In particular, at ANPRT, the five RRI pillars are generally considered in organising events, engaging different stakeholders or people not included in the organisations' staffs, since the beginning of the project in relation with public engagement issues.

ANPRT already has a public Ethical Code available at:

http://www.legislation.tn/detailtexte/D%C3%A9cret-num-2014-4030-du-03-10-2014-jort-2014-090_2014090040303

The Ethical Code focuses on values of the work in the public sector (the respect of law, the equality, the probity, the neutrality, the integrity, the efficiency, the assiduity, the accountability, private life) relationships among public officials (i) relationships of the public official with his superiors ii) relationships of the public officials with his colleagues iii) relationships of the public officials with his subordinates) and on relationships between a public official and her or his environment (i) relationships with the citizens ii) the public official and media). The team involved in R&I-PEERS is aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules have been taken into account in mentoring and coaching activities related to: workshops, training, web site, social media. The actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people at ANPRT by contributing to the general atmosphere and feeling change on Gender equality, the gender equality issues are discussed not only by woman, but the discussion is also wider and is related to potential measures and solutions. ANPRT follows a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data and the organized activities are documented with the informed consent of the participants, however, this practice is, in general, not widespread enough in the work culture.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, ANPRT built a gender-balanced project team in R&I-PEERS, is producing an annual statistics report, and adopts flexible working hours (on-line working). Furthermore, ANPRT has also succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures. The activities in R&I-PEERS had Beneficial effects in stimulating equal participant and including

gender perspectives. In fact, involving different gender perspective facilitated real participation of staff members in work, since factors such as work-life balance were better taken into account.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, ANPRT frequently provided the project’s outputs freely accessible: Statistics, Leaflets, Roll-up, videos, web site, social media. The ANPRT GEP is not publicly available at the moment, because ANPRT will make it open when the stabilized and final version will be available.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, ANPRT carried out 12 different public engagement activities that are considered satisfying. These activities did not produce any change or deviation in the activities or practice in the organisation. The initiatives were addressed to intersect ANPRT activities with similar activities or initiatives of National public authorities (Ministry of Woman, Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Ministry of Finance, NGOs (Learned society...), Media (radio, social media...). The outcomes have highlighted the benefit in organising these initiatives (workshops, conferences, public events...) jointly with other events at the local, regional, national and European levels.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, ANPRT is active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy also with the contribution of the R&I-PEERS project, by organizing Workshops, training sessions, animation of R&I-PEERS desk, participation to conferences. The ANPRT community (internal and external) shows interest in gender-related events and these activities help raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization	
General issues about RRI	
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?	
<i>Familiar</i>	
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?	
<i>Frequently</i>	
If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how	
<i>Organising events, engaging different stakeholders or people not included in the organisations' staffs, since the beginning of the project in relation to public engagement issues.</i>	
Ethics	
Has your organization an Ethical code	
<i>Yes</i>	
If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS	
<p><i>CODE OF CONDUCT AND ETHICS OF THE PUBLIC OFFICIAL:</i></p> <p>http://www.legislation.tn/detailtexte/D%C3%A9cret-num-2014-4030-du-03-10-2014-jort-2014-090_2014090040303</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Values of the work in the public sector: The respect of law, The equality, The probity, The neutrality, The integrity, The efficiency, The assiduity, The accountability, Private life</i> - <i>Relationships among public officials: i) Relationships of the public official with his superiors ii) Relationships of the public officials with his colleagues iii) Relationships of the public officials with his subordinates</i> 	

- <i>The public official and his environment: i) Relationships with the citizens ii) the public official and media</i>
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?
<i>Aware</i>
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
Event: Workshops, training, web site, social media...
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
Mentoring, coaching
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, please specify:
<i>Building gender-balanced project teams, Annual statistics report, Flexible working hours (On-line working)</i>
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
<i>Yes</i>
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<i>Statistics, Leaflets, Roll-up, videos, web site, social media...</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
<i>2</i>
Conferences:
<i>0</i>
Interviews:
<i>0</i>
Participatory events:
<i>5</i>
Surveys:
<i>1</i>
Social media:
<i>3</i>
Other:
<i>1</i>
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?

<i>Satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>No</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>Yes</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, Please, specify
<i>Workshops, animation of R&I-PEERS desk, participation to conferences...</i>

RRI and GEP in your organization
Ethics
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?
<i>Much</i>
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution
<i>the general atmosphere and feeling on Gender equality issues are changing, the gender equality issues are discussed not only by woman, but the discussion also is wider and is related to potential measures and solutions</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered
<i>This practice is not widespread enough in the work culture.</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Some time</i>
Please, explain what are the difficulties in adopting a responsible process (if any)
<i>No mastery of EU practices.</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Very Frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Beneficial</i>

For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
<i>involving different gender perspective facilitated real participation of staff members in work since factors such as work-life balance were better taken into account</i>
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
<i>I do not know</i>
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
<i>No</i>
If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>-</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
<i>We are waiting for the stabilized and final version</i>
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
<i>Yes</i>
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Very beneficial</i>
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>National public authorities (Ministry of Woman, Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Ministry of Finance, NGOs (Learned society...), Media (radio, social media...)</i>
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
<i>Organising initiatives (workshops, conferences, public events....) jointly with other events at the local level, at the regional level, at the national level or European level</i>
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Some time</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation
<i>Workshops and Training sessions</i>
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
<i>Yes</i>
If Yes, please specify:
<i>Awareness of gender issues and instilling gender culture in daily practices.</i>

<p>If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)</p>
<p><i>Raising awareness of the relevance of gender equality in science education practices</i></p>

4.10 GENERAL SECRETARIAT FOR FAMILY POLICY & GENDER EQUALITY (GSFPGE)

GSFPGE is a pilot organisation in R&I-PEERS. GSFPGE is little familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation and did not take into account the RRI pillars in R&I-PEERS activities.

The GSFPGE does not have a public Ethical Code and the team involved in R&I-PEERS is little aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research. The ethical rules have been taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project activities such as seminars. These activities produced an impact (evolution) clarifying the concept of work-life balance both for male and female employees and for the administration. GSFPGE follows, each time in R&I-PEERS, a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data and the organized activities are documented with the informed consent distributed and signed by the participants. Ethic requirements were also followed for all the surveys and questionnaires.

Regarding the pillar of Gender equality, GSFPGE within R&I-PEERS adopted gender-neutral language in public documents. Furthermore, the GSFPGE has also succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and people enjoyed equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures. The activities in R&I-PEERS had very beneficial effects in stimulating equal participant and including gender perspectives. In fact, male employees' hesitations about the need for equal participation were overcome.

Regarding the pillar of Open access, GSFPGE provided the project's outputs such as Questionnaires, the Project website and the GEP freely accessible. In particular, the GEP is accessible in the project website.

Regarding the pillar of Public engagement, GSFPGE did not carry out specific activities of public engagement in the context of R&I-PEERS, however frequently reached out people external to the organisation with other modalities like contacts with Sister projects, relationships with local NGOs by cooperating in joint seminars (e.g. at designing policy) at the national level.

Finally, regarding the pillar of Science education, GSFPGE is not active in organizing activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy.

RRI in the R&I-PEERS project and your organization
General issues about RRI
To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?
<i>A little familiar</i>
Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?
<i>Never</i>
Ethics
Has your organization an Ethical code
<i>No</i>
If No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities'

Yes,
Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?
<i>A little aware</i>
What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Not applicable</i>
What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?
<i>Seminars</i>
Gender equality
The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?
Yes
If Yes, please specify:
Gender-neutral language in public documents
Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?
<i>Involved</i>
In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?
Yes
Open access
Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)
<i>Frequently</i>
What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?
<i>Questionnaire, Project website</i>
Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)
<i>Not applicable</i>
Public engagement
How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?
Workshops/seminars:
-
Conferences:
-
Interviews:
0
Participatory events:
0
Surveys:
-
Social media:
-
Other:
0
Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?

<i>Moderately satisfying</i>
Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?
<i>No</i>
Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and the society)
Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?
<i>No</i>
To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?
<i>Rarely</i>
If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?
<i>No</i>

RRI and GEP in your organization
Ethics
How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?
<i>Enough</i>
If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution
<i>The concept of work-life balance became much clearer both for male and female employees and for the administration.</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?
<i>Each time</i>
When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?
<i>Each time</i>
Gender equality
Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?
<i>Very frequently</i>
As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?
<i>Very beneficial</i>
For answers 2-A little beneficial, 3-Neutral, 4-Beneficial, and 5-Very beneficial, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.
<i>Male employees' hesitations about the need for equal participation were overcome.</i>
Open access
Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow
<i>I do not know</i>
Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?
<i>Yes</i>

If Yes, where did you make it accessible?
<i>It is accessible on the Project Website</i>
If No, why you did not open the GEP?
-
If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?
-
Public engagement
Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
<i>Frequently</i>
If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?
Beneficial
Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
Sister Projects, NGOs
Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP
Cooperating in joint seminars (e.g. at designing policy) at national level
Science Education
Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy?
<i>Never</i>
Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization?
<i>No</i>

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This document analysed data related to the adoption of RRI in R&I-PEERS, considering the five pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation during the project activities within the overall consortium, i.e. piloting and no piloting partners. This should improve the positive impact of the project, as intrinsically RRI enables "governing innovation through early 'upstream' interventions rather than 'downstream' monitoring and 'correction' of interventions ex-post" [8]. The survey outcomes are stimulating the R&I-PEERS consortium to improve the RRI approach adoption along with the project life, as this enables to consider Gender equality using an eco-systemic approach, where the different pillars of RRI contribute and influence the changes in Gender equality.

Analysing data collected shows that all partners have a level of familiarity with RRI that is in the range from “Neutral” to “Very familiar”, except for GSFPGE that wrote to be "A little familiar" with RRI, as it is an organization that is not directly related to research (University or an RPO/RFO), but a governmental organization for promoting gender equality in general. In any case, GSFPGE usually carry out their activities following many of concepts of the five RRI pillars (with the exception for Science education, as it is not included in the focus of the organisation). All data collected in this survey will be complemented by the objective data and statistics collected within the different organisations involved in R&I-PEERS, by

the activities carried out within the different GEPs and, with the survey addressed to the staff of the different piloting organisations.

Now the main issues related to the five pillars of RRI are discussed.

Concerning Ethics, it is observed that all organizations adopt behaviours that follow practices or guidelines dictated by an ethical code. Only three organizations do not have a formalized Ethical Code, but they follow good internal practices within the organization. The R&I-PEERS project represents an opportunity for discussing to improve the adoption of shared ethical standards in the various organizations and, where possible, to promote the formulation of public code of ethics, highlighting the peculiarities that characterize the different types of organization also considering their geographical location and the type of activities they generally carry out. The activities in R&I-PEERS involved people in the different organisations independently from the gender and, this is producing a change in the mindset of people involved that is a key factor for pushing to overcome many stereotypes, for example, the idea that gender issues are discussed only by women.

In the second period of the project, we aim to reinforce the knowledge of the RRI approach, as it suggests building a holistic process where the Gender equality dimension and GEPs are developed also considering the other pillars of RRI as key factors for producing real changes in the organisations and in the people mindset.

In the next period, it has been suggested to adopt within R&I-PEERS some practices such as "An interactive and collaborative work (online) on documents with associated discussion, so that opinions can be considered". This suggestion is also very significant considering that the COVID 19 crisis requires an effort for adopting any type of collaboration that enables sharing ideas and contents processes. This could be done scheduling and organising periodic on-line working meetings, webinars, among the partners and also involving external stakeholders. This kind of initiatives can be also useful to strengthen research integrity implementing networking, open communication and information sharing, also heightening the principles of research integrity for future generations of researchers. One partner underlined the importance of providing concrete examples and best practices in research integrity to integrate this notion into the mindset of the researchers and for this purpose, it is necessary to give concrete examples also within the GEPs to be presented and disseminate in any initiative organised. Owing to the target of R&I-PEERS, which is on Gender equality, "research integrity" has to be presented considering all the previous cited issues, but always under the lens of *Gender equality*. *In this respect, the R&I-PEERS activities can help us in extracting lessons learned and "good practices" in defining and implementing the project activities and the GEPs.*

Concerning Gender equality, the entire project is related to this axis. However, with respect to this key issue, we are trying to understand if gender equality and equal treatment practices have been used by the partnership within the project, and if GEPs implementation is inclusive and enough beneficial. All partners have made an effort for building gender-balanced teams working in R&I-PEERS, to overcome the stereotypes that consider gender issues only of interest for women. Some partners also underlined that using a gender balance criterion when working in new projects has been generalised in the organisation as a good practice.

All partners put attention in providing equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures for people involved in R&I-PEERS activities.

The R&I-PEERS partners observed that the project had Beneficial or Very beneficial effects concerning Gender equality, stimulating equal participant and including gender perspectives in the work organisation. The activities of the project produced concrete consequences in the pilot organisations, as new practices and work organisation have been established (for example flexible working hours, teleworking, smart working). We need to observe that the worldwide crisis produced by COVID-19 is

deeply impacting in the work-life organisation and is also opening new challenges that could be interesting to discuss in the next period in the project.

The discussion related to the outcomes of the project and on the emerging challenges can be addressed promoting a strong action taking into account of the need: 1) to make open the outcomes and the discussions, 2) to involve people, organisations and projects also external with respect to the R&I-PEERS project, enlarging the points of view and enlarging the impacts of the project, 3) to reinforce the science education actions to improve the gender perspective in the research activities also.

Open access is a very important key for establishing a common and shared knowledge and to build a collective awareness related to Gender equality and research. All partners are sharing as much as possible information and documents related to the project. Not all organisations have explicit policies on Open access. Not all the GEPs have been made accessible in the first period. In the second period of the project, it is important to reinforce the openness of the GEPs and of practices that are enabling the different organisations to implement them, to provide good examples and to suggest good practices that also other organisations can follow. This can produce a snowball effect and can have an impact from territorial to international level. The production of open scientific publication will also reinforce the impact on the scientific community.

Concerning Public engagement, all the organisation carried out their activities involving internal staff, but also other stakeholders, establishing relationships at local, national and international level with the different actors (quadruple helix actors) and sisters' projects. Activities of public engagement are very important in order to collect a feedback from the involved actors and, to propose R&I-PEERS as an example for other experiences influencing opinions and other activities. Indeed, "*Some institutional changes are easier to implement if we can show that other RPOs are going in the same direction*". Public engagement has not produced very significant changes till now in the R&I-PEERS project or in the organisations involved in the public engagement process. However, during the first period of the project many activities were concentrated in the definition and approval of GEPs and the GEPs activities started in the spring of 2019. Currently, all the GEPs activities are running and public engagement will be crucial in the remaining time of the project. During the first two years of the project, the Public engagement initiatives were essentially organised using face-to-face methodologies. With the beginning of 2020, the COVID-19 crisis will ask everybody for implementing Public engagement using not only face-to-face, but also virtual meetings, webinars, etc.. These could be co-organised with other actors or other projects both in local language and in English. Many of these online activities can leave a trace that can also be used to compose sharing and training courses that are available for the different actors involved and for the entire society.

That is, Open access, Public engagement and Science education are deeply connected. Not all the partners of R&I-PEERS usually organize activities related to science education, even if all organised at least some activity in the framework of the project. These activities till now were usually done at local or national level. In the next period, it could be useful to organise a Science education initiative that enables an exchange of experiences at the European level. This initiative could be organised on-line.

6 REFERENCES AND SITOGRAPHY

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7 Appendix I – Questionnaires

7.1 QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PILOTING PARTNERS

Part 1 – Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project (not directly connected to the activities carried out in the GEP), related to your organisation

General Issues about RRI

1) To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?

1-Not at all 2-A little familiar 3-neutral 4- Familiar 5-Very familiar

2) Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

2.1) If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how.

.....

(e.g. organising events, following ethical behaviours as suggested in the Grant Agreement, engaging public in the project initiatives, or, engaging different stakeholders or people not included in the organisations' staffs, since the beginning of the project in relation with public engagement issues, following ethical issues, etc.)

Ethics

3) Has your organization an Ethical code

Yes, No, I do not know

3.1) If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.

.....

3.2) if No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities

Yes No I do not know

4) Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?

1-Not at all 2-A little aware 3-neutral 4- Aware 5-Very aware

Definition

“Research integrity is generally understood to mean the performance of research according to the highest standards of professionalism and rigour, in an ethically robust manner. The behaviours espoused by ethics and research integrity should ensure the accuracy and truth of the research recorded in publications and elsewhere” [9]

5)What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?

..... (Please see “Good Research Practices” at: [10])

6)What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?

.....

Gender equality

7) The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?

Yes, No, I do not Know

7.1) If Yes, please specify:

.....

(e.g. • building gender-balanced project teams • organizing work according to family-friendly work spaces, etc.)

8) Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?

1-not at all, 2- slightly involved 3- moderately involved 4- Involved, 5- Strongly involved

9) In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?

Yes, No, I do not Know

9.1) If No, please specify:

..... (for example: Some people enjoyed greater privileges because of...)

Open access

10) Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

10.1) If you answered Never, do you believe that in the future you will make public your outputs

Yes, No, I do not Know

11) What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?

.....

12) Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)

.....

Public engagement

13) How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?

- Workshops/seminars, -----
- conferences, -----
- interviews, -----
- Participatory events -----
- surveys, -----
- social media, -----
- other, -----
- No one

14) Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?

1- Not at all, 2- slightly satisfying, 3- moderately satisfying, 4- satisfying, 5- very satisfying

15) Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?

Yes, No, I do not know

15.1) If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:

.....

Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)

16) Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?

Yes, No, I do not know

17) To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts??

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

17.1) If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?

Yes, No

17.1.1) If Yes, Please, specify

.....

Part 2 – Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project, related to your GEP activities

Ethics

18) How much do you believe that the actions planned and implemented within the GEP are producing an evolution of the societal values that inspire the behaviour of people in your organization?

1- A little, 2- Enough, 3- Neutral, 4- Much, 5- Very much

18.1) If you answered: 2- Enough, or 3- Neutral, or 4- Much, or 5- Very much, please, describe the values evolution

.....

(E.g. the general atmosphere and feeling on Gender equality issues are changing, the gender equality issues are discussed not only by woman, the discussion is wider and is related to inequalities and potential solutions, etc.)

19) When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you follow a responsible process of communication and information asking for informed consent for images or personal data?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Each time

19.1) If you answered: 1- Never, or 2- Rarely, or 3- Some time, or 4- Frequently, please, specify what are the difficulties encountered

.....

20) When you planned and implemented the activities related to the GEP in your organization, did you adopt a responsible process for managing data following National and European laws and GDPR?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Each time

20.1) Please, explain what are the difficulties in adopting a responsible process (if any)

.....

Gender equality

21) Did you try to stimulate equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives among of staff members as part of GEP implementation in your organisation?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

22) As a part of GEP implementation in your organisation, how beneficial do you believe stimulating equal participation and inclusion of gender perspectives was for staff members?

1-Not at all 2-A little beneficial 3-neutral 4- Beneficial 5-Very beneficial

22.1) For answers 2-5, please describe how stimulating equal participation and including gender perspectives through implementing the GEP was beneficial for staff members.

.....(e.g. involving different gender perspective facilitated real participation of staff members in work, since factors such as work-life balance were better taken into account, etc.)

Open access

23) Has your organization established Open Access practices to follow

Yes, No, I do not know

24) Did you make open accessible the GEP defined in your organisation?

Yes, No

24.1) If Yes, where did you make it accessible?

.....

24.2) If No, why you did not open the GEP?

.....

24.3) If No, do you think that you will make the GEP open accessible?

Yes, No, I do not know

Public engagement

25) Did you reach out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

25.1) If you answered:2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, how much do you believe beneficial was reaching out people external to the organisation (and, not only your staff, etc. – for example, reaching families or friends of your staff members) with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP?

1-Not at all 2-A little beneficial 3-neutral 4- Beneficial 5-Very beneficial

25.1.1) Please, describe who did you reach out externally to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP (e.g. Local public authorities, NGOs, Citizens associations, Media, etc.)

.....

25.1.2) Please, describe how do you believe beneficial reaching out people external to the organisation with initiatives, information, etc. related to the implementation of your GEP

.....

(e.g. organising initiatives jointly with other events at the local level, at the regional level, at the national level or European level, etc.... specify what kind of initiatives)

Science Education

26) Are there any activities planned in your organization’s GEP that are related to science education and raising science literacy??

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

26.1) If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, please, describe what kind of activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions did you include in GEP implementation

.....

(Workshops, webinars, masters, etc.)

27) Did GEP activities related to gender equality issues in science education prove beneficial in your organization??

Yes No

27.1) if yes, please specify

.....

27.2) If Yes, please, describe why do you believe that including any activity that addresses the Gender equality issues in Science education actions within the activities of GEP implementation was beneficial (e.g. raising awareness of relevance of gender equality in science education practices; increasing competence of educators to be sensitive to the importance of gender dimension in science and research, etc..)

.....

7.2 QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ORGANISATION WHO ARE PARTNERS IN R&I-PEERS BUT ARE NOT IMPLEMENTING THE GEP IN R&I -PEERS

General Issues about RRI

1) To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?

1-Not at all 2-A little familiar 3-neutral 4- Familiar 5-Very familiar

2) Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-PEERS project from the beginning?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

2.1) If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how.

.....

(e.g. organising events, following ethical behaviours as suggested in the Grant Agreement, engaging public in the project initiatives, or engaging different stakeholders or people not included in the organisations' staffs, since the beginning of the project in relation with public engagement issues, following ethical issues, etc. .)

Ethics

3) Has your organization an Ethical code

Yes, No, I do not know

3.1) If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-PEERS.

.....

3.2) if No, did you follow in any case ethical practices during the project activities

Yes No I do not know

4) Are the staff members, who are involved in R&I-PEERS, aware of the principles that regulate the integrity of research?

1-Not at all 2-A little aware 3-neutral 4- Aware 5-Very aware

Definition

“Research integrity is generally understood to mean the performance of research according to the highest standards of professionalism and rigour, in an ethically robust manner. The behaviours espoused by ethics and research integrity should ensure the accuracy and truth of the research recorded in publications and elsewhere” [9]

5)What kind of practices did you use to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?

.....

(Please see “Good Research Practices” at: [10])

6)What kind of practices do you believe could be useful introduce to promote research integrity principles in the R&I-PEERS activities?

.....

Gender equality

7) The R&I-PEERS project is about implementing Gender Equality Plans. Have any gender equality practices from the project regarding staff and working conditions been adopted?

Yes, No, I do not Know

7.1) If Yes, please, specify:

.....

(e.g. • build a project gender-balanced team • organise the work according to a family-friendly work spaces, etc.)

8) Outside the scope of GEP implementation, has the R&I-PEERS project succeeded in reaching external people in promoting equal participation and including gender perspectives?

1-not at all, 2- slightly involved 3- moderately involved 4- Involved, 5- Strongly involved

9) In addition to gender, did people enjoy equal treatment during the R&I-PEERS project, as concerns ethnicity, creed and other diversity measures?

Yes, No, I do not Know

9.1) If No, please, specify:

.....

(for example: Some people had much more privileges than others because of the general existing situation...)

Open access

10) Did you make the outputs of the work in the R&I-PEERS project freely available? (e.g. deliverables, leaflets, posters, videos, articles in proceedings of conferences, articles in journals, etc.)

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

10.1) If you answered Never, do you believe that in the future you will make public your outputs

Yes, No, I do not Know

11) What document or information have you made public in R&I-PEERS (list them)?

.....

12) Please, indicate why you did not make public some document or information (if any)

.....

Public engagement

13) How many of the following public engagement activities did your organisation carry out (organized) in R&I-PEERS (excluding engagement for GEPs implementation in your organization)?

- Workshops/seminars, -----
- conferences, -----
- interviews, -----
- Participatory events -----
- surveys, -----

- social media, -----
- other, -----
- No one

14) Are Public engagement actions implemented in the project satisfying?

1- Not at all, 2- slightly satisfying, 3- moderately satisfying, 4- satisfying, 5- very satisfying

15) Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?

Yes, No, I do not know

15.1) If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:

.....

Science education (Universities don't have to fill this part related to science education)

16) Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?

Yes, No, I do not know

17) To which extent R&I-PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?

1- Never, 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently

17.1) If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-PEERS?

Yes, No

17.1.1) If Yes, Please, specify

.....

8 Appendix II – RRI on-line survey

Each partner can fill in the survey on-line at: <https://www.ripgep.eu/registeredarea/rriSurvey>

One person per partner is enabled to fill in this survey for the year 2019. Once you are connected you can see the following figure.

This survey has to collect data for the validation check with respect to the adoption of the principles of Responsible Research and innovation during the activities of the project. This in accordance with the Task 7.3 “RRI validation check” of “WP7- Dissemination and impact creation”. This survey has been defined for analysing how the five pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) - i.e. Ethics, Gender equality, Open access, Public engagement and Science education - are kept in the activities of the R&I-Peers project accordingly to the guidelines of the European Commission (EC).

RRI addresses research and the project activities according to an approach that has to be safe, ethically acceptable, and responding to the societal and people needs and expectations and, it aims at aligning research and innovation changes within societal values. The EC defines RRI [<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>] as “a process where all societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations etc.) work together during the whole R&I process in order to better align R&I outcomes to the values, needs and expectations of European society.

“RRI consists of designing and implementing R&I policy that will:

- o engage society more broadly in its research and innovation activities,
- o increase access to scientific results,
- o ensure gender equality, in both the research process and research content,
- o take into account the ethical dimension, and promote formal and informal science education.”

[<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/science-and-society>]

Why observing the R&I-Peers Project implementation under the lens of RRI?

This is because RRI enables “governing innovation through early ‘upstream’ interventions rather than ‘downstream’ monitoring and ‘correction’ of interventions ex post”. Genus, Audley & Iskandarova, Marfuga, 2018. “Responsible innovation: its institutionalisation and a critique,” Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Elsevier, vol. 128(C), pages 1-9.]

This means that the approach followed in planning and carrying out the R&I-Peers project activities adopts the five RRI pillars. In particular, this survey is administrated both:

- 1) to the five pilot organizations (Research Performing Organizations, and Research Funding Organizations) and,
- 2) to the other partners of the consortium.

In particular, the survey enables the R&I-Peers consortium to use the RRI approach along the project life. All the consortium members are asked to contribute in this data collection. Each partner had to fill in only one time the questionnaire. The answer can be discussed internally by each organisation and one person will provide the answer for the organisation. The survey is different for organisations that are implementing the GEPs (Pilot organisations) with respect to the other partners that are not implementing them. In particular, pilot organisations are invited to provide both,

- 1) information on Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-Peers project (not directly connected to the activities carried out in the GEP), related to your organisation,
- 2) information on the use of the Responsible Research and Innovation principles in the R&I-Peers project, related to your GEP activities, while partners that do not implement the GEP will be invited to provide only information on RRI related to their activity in the project.

The next section (2.1) provides the survey to be filled in by the pilot partners, while section 2.2 describes the survey to be filled in by the remaining partners.

2019 2020

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The answer can be discussed internally by each organisation and one person will provide the answer for the organisation. The survey is different for organisations that are implementing the GEPs (Pilot organisations that are ANPRT, CIC nanoGUNE, CNTI, GSFPGE, MIGAL, UNISA, ZRC Sazu) with respect to the other partners that are not implementing them.

Each partner is asked to provide the answers by 15th of May 2020. For any doubt, please contact Patrizia Grifoni at: patrizia.grifoni@irpps.cnr.it

In particular, pilot organisations are invited to provide both,

1. information on Responsible Research and Innovation in the R&I-PEERS project (not directly connected to the activities carried out in the GEP), related to your organisation,
2. information on the use of the Responsible Research and Innovation principles in the R&I-PEERS project, related to your GEP activities, while partners that do not implement the GEP will be invited to provide only information on RRI related to their activity in the project.

For this reason, If you are a partner that is implementing the GEP in R&I-PEERS (pilot partners are ANPRT, CIC nanoGUNE, CNTI, GSFPGE, MIGAL, UNISA, ZRC Sazu), firstly you have to click on the button “RRI in the R&I peers project and your organisation” and fill in this part and, save it. Secondly, you have to click on the button “RRI and GEP in your organisation” and then you have to fill in the questionnaire.

If you are a partner that is NOT implementing the GEP you have to click on the button “RRI in the R&I peers project and your organisation” (that is the only one option that you can see) and then you have to fill in the questionnaire and save it.

The next section (2.1) provides the survey to be filled in by the pilot partners, while section 2.2 describes the survey to be filled in by the remaining partners.

2019 2020

1 2

DELETE SURVEY 2019 EDIT DATE

RRI in the R&I peers project and your organization RRI and GEP in your organization

General issues about RRI

To what extent are you familiar with the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)?
Very familiar

Were RRI pillars taken into account in the R&I-Peers project from the beginning?
Frequently

If you selected one of the following responses: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, then explain how

(e.g. organising events, following ethical behaviours as suggested in the Grant agreement, engaging public in the project initiatives, engaging different stakeholders or people not included in the organisations' staffs, since the beginning of the project in relation with public engagement issues, following ethical issues, ...)

Ethics

Has your organization an Ethical code
Yes

If Yes, specify the link to the document (if any) and what are the relevant ethical practices suggested in that code that you followed during the activities in R&I-Peers.

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Once you have provided your answers, you can save your responses. You can complete your responses in multiple sessions, i.e. you can provide some answers, save them and the day after you can complete your answers connecting yourself again and saving again at the end.

Has public engagement produced any change or deviation in the activities or practices during the project?

Select ▼

If Yes, please, specify the changes or deviations produced:

Science education (Universities need to consider their activities concerning science education also addressed to a non-academic target and to the society)

Does your organization organize any activities dedicated to science education, popularization of science and improvement of science literacy?

Select ▼

To which extent RI PEERS project activities at your organization contribute to its science education efforts?

Select ▼

If Yes, Please, specify

a

If you answered: 2- Rarely, 3- Some time, 4- Frequently, 5- Very frequently, have you done science education activities in R&I-Peers?

Select ▼

SAVE

Note that your responses are saved on a secure server managed by CNR. For any question do not hesitate to contact Patrizia Grifoni at: patrizia.grifoni@irpps.cnr.it.